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Research Article

**FORMULATION AND CHARACTERIZATION OF
LIDOCAINE HYDROCHLORIDE MICROGEL FOR BETTER
ANTI-INFLAMMATORY ACTIVITY**

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Abstract:

The aim of study was to conduct the formulation and evaluation of Microgel of Lidocaine Hydrochloride by single dispersion method. Drug Lidocaine Hydrochloride and polymers Carbopol and HPMC were taken in different ratios for preparing five microgel formulations. The prepared microgel were characterised by for pH, viscosity, spreadability, particle size distribution, poly dispersity index and in vitro drug permeation studies. On the basis of various evaluation parameters formulation F2 was selected as the optimized formulation with particle size 14.25nm, zeta potential -12.45, PDI 0.163. Drug content of the prepared microgel was found to be 93.7% and the percentage drug release as 83.45% in 8 hours study period.

Keywords: Microgel, Lidocaine HCl, Particle size, Zeta potential, Polymers

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INTRODUCTION:

Pain control is an integral part of modern medical science. Needle injection of local anaesthetic is the most common modality of pain control used today. The actual method of giving anaesthetic is painful because of stimulation produced by the needle during insertion and injection of the anaesthetic solution. For a comfortable treatment, it is important to have pain free method of administering local anaesthetic [1].

Lidocaine Hydrochloride which is used as local anaesthetic act by blocking the transmission of signals from the terminal fibres of the sensory nerves, control pain perception and alter the pain reaction of an individual. One of the benefits of topical anaesthetics is effective anaesthesia for certain procedures with little to no systemic exposure to the agents. The anaesthesia produced by lidocaine is faster, more intense, longer lasting

and more extensive than the produced by an equal concentration of procedure [2].

Microgels are the most immersing and advanced drug delivery system whose particle size ranging from 10-100 μ m. Due to their small size, lower surface tension and high amount of dissolvability and permeation it is immensely used in delivery of drug as a targeted delivery system to a specific organ and improves the bioavailability and therapeutic effect of drug[3].

MATERIAL AND METHOD:**Material**

Lidocaine hydrochloride was obtained as a gift sample from Nectar Life Sciences Ltd, Punjab. Carbopol 934, HPMCK4M, Tween 80, Ethanol, Propylene Glycol, Triethonalamine was obtained from Central Drug House Pvt.Ltd,India.

Table 1: Formulation table for preparation of microgel of Lidocaine HCL

Ingredients	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
Lidocaine HCl(mg)	100	100	100	100	100
Carbopol (mg)	200	300	400	300	200
HPMC(mg)	100	200	300	200	100
Ethanol(ml)	30	40	30	40	30
Tween 20(%)	2.5	2.5	2	1.5	1.5
Propylene Glycol(%)	5	10	15	6	8
Triethonalamine	qs	qs	qs	qs	qs

Method**Identification of drug:**

Identification of Lidocaine Hydrochloride was carried out by Infra-red spectroscopy (FTIR) and compared with standard IR spectrum of Lidocaine Hydrochloride[4].

Fig.1: IR spectra of Lidocaine Hydrochloride

Preparation of standard curve of Lidocaine HCl in Ethanol.

50 mg drug was accurately weighed and transferred to 50 ml of volumetric flask and dissolved in 50ml of solvent. From the stock solution dilutions having concentration 5 μ g/ml, 10 μ g/ml, 15 μ g/ml, 20 μ g/ml, 25 μ g/ml, 30 μ g/ml (Beer's range 5-30 μ g/ml) was prepared. These dilutions were observed in UV Spectrophotometer and absorbance was measured [5].

Table 2

Table 2: Standard curve data of Lidocaine HCl in ethanol

Concentration (μ g/ml)	Absorbance in ethanol
0	0.000
5	0.114
10	0.214
15	0.311
20	0.415
25	0.521
30	0.612

Fig.2: Standard curve of Lidocaine HCL in ethanol

Procedure:

Microgel formulation was prepared by single dispersion technique. The polymers are mixed with water with vigorous stirring and left for 30 minutes for dissolving the polymer. To the polymer solution drug were added and mixed well with continuous stirring. To that the mixture of surfactant and co-surfactant (tween 20 and ethanol) was slowly added with continuous stirring at 800rpm. Required quantity of propylene glycol was added. After complete dispersion, the pH of gel was adjusted by using triethonalamine. Distilled water was added and made upto the volume [6].

EVALUATION OF MICROGEL**1. Determination of pH-**

The pH of the prepared microgel was determined using calibrated digital pH meter. In this method 1gm of microgel was added and dissolved in 100ml distilled water and kept for 2 hours. Then, the pH of the following medium was measured using digital pH meter [7].

2. Viscosity-

Viscosity of the prepared Microgel was evaluated using Brookfield viscometer. The prepared microgel was subjected to different spindle at specific rpm. The data was collected during the procedure and a graph was prepared to determine the viscosity [8].

Fig 3

Fig.3: Graph of viscosity against rpm of the prepared Microgel

3. Spreadability study-

Spreadability defines the extent of the microgel spread onto the skin when applied. The method includes the use of two glass plates (20×20cm). Specific amount of prepared gel(1gm)was placed in one of the glass slide and then second glass was placed above it[9].

4. Particle Size, Zeta Potential and Poly Dispersity Index

Particle size and zeta potential of the microgel was determined by using Differential light scattering with a zetasizer (Malvern Instrument,UK). The micogel were dispersed into milique waater and diluted accordingly. This solution was then analysed using zetasizer for particle size and zeta potential[10].

Figures 4 to 7

Fig.4: Particle size distribution graph of formulation F1

Fig.5: Particle size distribution graph of formulation F2

Fig.6: Zeta potential graph of formulation F1

Fig.7: Zeta potential graph of formulation F2

5. Determination of Drug Content

For determination of drug content of the formulation 50mg drug equivalent to formulation was added into a 50ml volumetric flask containing 50ml of solvent in which both drug and polymer are soluble. The solution was shaken for 30 minutes and then kept for 24hrs. After 24hrs the dispersion was further shaken and then filtered. The resultant solution was then subjected to UV spectrophotometer at 263nm[11].

Table 3-5

Table 3: Particle size distribution of prepared gel

S.no	Formulation	Particle size(nm)	
		Diameter(nm)	%Intensity
1	F1	18.38	100%
2	F2	14.25	100%
3	F3	50.17	92.4%
4	F4	90.64	84.3%
5	F5	140.59	82.3%

Table4: Zeta potential and Poly Dispersity Index of prepared microgel

S.no	Formulation	Zeta potential	PDI
1	F1	-10.68	0.175
2	F2	-12.45	0.163
3	F3	-9.21	0.289
4	F4	-12.1	0.357
5	F5	-7.21	0.398

Table 5: Measurement of average Viscosity, pH, Spreadability, Drug content of the microgel formulation.

S.No	Formulation	pH	Spreadability	Viscosity(cps)	Drug content
1	F1	6.8±0.19	12.78±2.35	1693.8±3.85	91.72±4.3
2	F2	6.9±0.11	19.28±1.48	1894.3±2.43	93.7±1.9
3	F3	6.5±0.15	16.67±3.78	1484.1±5.28	90.56±3.2
4	F4	6.1±0.21	14.54±5.67	1595.1±5.97	88.34±2.1
5	F5	6.4 ± 0.14	13.67±4.32	1713.8±8.56	90.22±3.8

6. In vitro diffusion studies-

In vitro diffusion study was conducted to determine the release of drug from the formulation. In this technique a Franz diffusion cell was used. Phosphate buffer of pH 6.8 was used for in vitro release as receptor medium and the donor compartment is mounted with egg membrane. The microgel sample was applied on the membrane and then fixed in between donor and receptor membrane. The temperature of diffusion medium was thermostatically controlled at 37° by surrounding water in jacket and the medium was continuously stirred by magnetic stirrer at speed of 600 rpm. The sample at predetermined intervals were withdrawn and replaced by equal volume of freshly prepared fluid. The sample withdrawn were spectrophotometrically measured at 263nm against their blank[12].

Table 6

Table 6: In vitro zero order release profile for formulation F1-F5

Time	F1	F2	F3	F4	F5
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	30.12	34.48	25.16	22.67	18.25
2	38.01	47.07	38.67	30.34	25.38
3	46.59	55.21	40.18	39.85	36.56
4	54.36	62.32	51.16	45.91	48.37
5	62.15	69.85	56.37	58.15	56.25
6	69.42	73.38	64.17	64.42	63.46
7	75.32	78.84	72.18	70.32	67.20
8	79.78	83.45	77.91	74.78	73.68

7. Drug release kinetic study-

The drug release kinetic specifies the release mechanism of drug from microgel. The obtained release data was treated using following equation-

Zero order equation- the graph plotted between amounts of drug release versus time.

First order equation- graph between log cumulative percent of drug remaining versus time.

Higuchi equation- graph between cumulative percent of drug release versus square root of time.

Korsmeyer-Peppas equation- graph between log cumulative percent of drug release versus log time[13].

Table 7

Table 7: Comparison of correlation coefficient of release data of formulations.

Formulation	r ²			n ²	Best model fit	Mechanism of release
	Zero order	First order	Higuchi Kinetics			
F1	0.9254	0.9907	0.9178	0.4872	Zero order	Anomalous transport
F2	0.8664	0.9848	0.9311	0.4227	First order	Fickian Diffusion
F3	0.9404	0.9802	0.9133	0.5302	First order	Anomalous transport
F4	0.9612	0.9929	0.9113	0.6025	First order	Anomalous transport
F5	0.9699	0.9962	0.9148	0.7086	First order	Anomalous transport

Fig 8-11

Fig.8: In-vitro Zero order model for formulation F1-F5

Fig.9: In-vitro First order model for formulation F1-F5

Fig.10: In-vitro Higuchi model for formulation F1-F5

Fig.11: In-vitro Peppas model for formulation F1-F5

8.Ex-Vivo permeation study-

Ex-vivo studies was conducted using goat's skin membrane. Membrane is isolated and kept in Ringer solution overnight. The membrane was clamped between donor and receptor compartments of Franz diffusion cell. The receptor compartment was filled with phosphate buffer 7.4 and was stirred throughout the whole process. Appropriate (1ml) of sample were withdrawn from the receptor compartment at specific time intervals and were replaced with fresh buffer solution to maintain sink condition. After that samples were analysed for drug concentration using UV-Visible spectrophotometer at 263 nm and the cumulative drug release was determined [14].

Table 8

Fig 12

Table 8:Ex-Vivo permeation study.

Time (hrs)	%Drug permeation in-vitro	%Drug permeation ex-vivo
0	0	0
1	34.48	28.15
2	47.07	37.07
3	55.21	42.33
4	62.32	52.47
5	69.85	58.28
6	73.38	63.01
7	78.84	70.95
8	83.45	76.89

Fig.12: Ex-vivo-drug permeation study of optimized formulation

RESULT:

Five formulations were prepared among which formulation F2 was selected as optimized formulation because of its small particle size (275.8 d.nm) mid ranged polydispersity (PDI of 0.163), with zeta potential value -12.46mV which lies in the range of zeta potential (-15mV to + 15mV), it shows 83.45% drug release after 8 hours study. Drug release kinetics with model fitting was done. Zero- order, First-order, Higuchi matrix and Korsmeyer-Peppas equation models were tested among which the best fit was shown by First order. The mechanism of transport was by fickian diffusion (diffusion coefficient, $n=0.4227$).

CONCLUSION:

Lidocaine Hydrochloride is a local anaesthetics which is selected for the development of microgel as it compiles with physicochemical properties requires to permeate through skin. The microgel of lidocaine HCl was prepared by single diffusion method and evaluation parameter like pH, viscosity, spreadability, particle size, zeta potential, PDI, drug content and diffusion studies were done. All parameters were within a limit forming a clear gel. The finding of this study indicated that lidocaine hydrochloride microgel is efficient and safe and has wider prospects to be used as topical drug delivery system.

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